

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEAKING COMPETENCE THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND SELF-MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: In the article, the purpose, opportunities, results of education of students in the digital world and the competences of studying and working in the digital world are analyzed, in addition, the scientific-theoretical justification of the development of the structural components of students' speech competence in teaching the mother tongue, og scientific research of linguists and Methodist scientists on the development of oral and written speech, independent expression of one's opinion, development of creative approach to text creation and acquisition of speech culture views analysis done.

Keywords: Digital technology, digitization, digital transformation, competencies, literacy, digital literacy, digital ethics, speech, oral and written literacy, speaking skills, speaking competence, exercise, study assignment, work on the text.

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It is known that the role of speech competition is incomparable in making school-age students broad-minded and fluent in speech. Speaking and speaking skills are important in language teaching for several reasons. First of all, language is not just making sentences and speaking. Traditional grammar, linguistic tools and rules will not be sufficient for communication. Second, students need to learn how to compose written and spoken text that is consistent with ideas and concepts, and how to make these ideas coherent. At such a time, the right use of interactive technology tools can be of great benefit. In his coursework, the student used the ideas and research on speech composition of many research scholars, including Hymes, Canale, Saeed, and Congman, to illuminate speech composition.

Regarding digitization and learning in the digital world, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF 6079 of October 5, 2020 "On approval of the strategy "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" and measures for its implementation" states that "digitization in the digital world" , development of digital technologies , consideration of new projects in the field of digital economy and development of digital education" programs are being implemented.² In recent years, digitization has fundamentally changed the work and daily activities of a person. Digital transformation is reshaping society, the labor market, employers' demands and work activities. In the implementation of digital transformation in the educational system in our country, while using the advantages and opportunities, it

is necessary to effectively eliminate the risk of this digital transformation, that is, the gap between rural and urban areas.

Today's in the day remote the form of education is playing an important role in the world community. Of course, modern technology tools of the 21st century are of great importance in this. Effective use of digital learning tools in classrooms can increase student engagement, allow teachers to improve lesson plans, and personalize learning. As advances in technology drive globalization and digital transformation, educators can help students acquire the skills they need to succeed in their chosen fields in the future.

The design method is a teaching system in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and competences in the process of planning, constructing, and executing practical tasks that are continuously increasing in complexity. perform projects related to. In order for this method to be highly effective, students must have a high level of motivation in completing the project. The following personal competencies are formed: teamwork; diligence; sense of responsibility; self-confidence; teachability; quick thinking; being able to see the progress of the process; ability to observe; far away according to to know diagnosis .

Interactive approach _ Teachers create a comfortable environment for good organization of the lesson process. Students are allowed to exchange ideas (information). They discuss and resolve the pending issues together. They will find a solution in cooperation to get out of the situation . They demonstrate their knowledge to each other based on the information they have received . Sh . Sariyev's research shows that it is necessary for the teacher to take the lesson seriously in order to develop students' speaking competences. In order to read the text in the lesson , the teacher should prepare thoroughly, try to understand the content more deeply, determine how certain parts of the text should be read. After the teacher explains how to read some sounds, syllables, words, students read the text in turn. The teacher follows them and corrects them" The teacher should read the words as in the brochure, pay attention to intonation and stress while reading the words, pronounce the lexical units in the sentences clearly and fluently. teaching, students' acquisition of reading techniques asset to the situation will change .

Digital literacy is modern is a set of knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for life in the world , for safe and effective use of digital technologies and Internet resources. Creating and maintaining dynamic online profiles is the ability to manage large and complex online social networks.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of digital economy and electronic government", the widespread introduction of digital technologies at all

stages of the education system in our country and the improvement of the level of digital knowledge necessary for the modern economy, the improvement of the educational infrastructure, as well as within the framework of the implementation of the "Five Initiatives" project, until 2022, digital knowledge training centers will be established in all regions of the republic to open in the eye caught

Digital literacy is _ refers to the core set of knowledge, skills , and attitudes that enable a person to effectively solve problems in a digital environment .

Digital Literacy Components:

- Information literacy

characteristics of information and its various sources

Skills to find and compare relevant information

Responding to the benefits and harms of information

Computer literacy

Knowing the computer device and its functions

Skills in using computers and similar devices

Attitudes about the role of the computer in everyday practice

Media literacy

Information about media content and sources

News research and fact - checking skills

Attitude to the reliability of the information conveyed through mass media

Communicative literacy

Knowledge of the specifics of communication in digital communication

Skills of using modern means of communication

Attitudes towards communication ethics and norms in the digital environment

Technological innovation

Knowledge of current technological trends

Skills in working with gadgets and applications

Technological innovations advantages about views _

if a person wanted thing if he cannot say it , he will not be able to compete equally with others, use the usual forms of communication and will have to resort to some other forms of controlling his voice, sometimes using violence and force. Based on this, it is necessary to properly organize the correction of speech development of an individual from an early age . "Early Start" has a positive effect on the acceptance of the mother tongue and the subsequent acquisition of any other language .

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